

IMPACTS OF YOUTH EMPOWERMENT PROGRAMMES IN ABAK LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

Mboho, Kingdom Sunday
Department of Sociology and Anthropology,
Akwa Ibom State University, Ikot Akpaden.
Kmboho360@gmail.com. 08024144507

John, Mfonobong Monday
Department of Sociology and Anthropology,
Akwa Ibom State University, Ikot Akpaden.
Mfonobongj20@gmail.com. 08084152528

Abstract

The Nigerian government through its various agencies, nongovernmental organizations, and even private philanthropists, have resorted to committing a lot of resources to training and empowering the youths in various entrepreneurships. This is done with the aim of enhancing creation of jobs, reduction of poverty, and generation of income both to individuals and government thereby bringing about economic diversification which will help reduce overdependence on government and oil revenue, hence leading to national development. This study therefore empirically examined whether empowering the youths has significantly contributed to the growth and development of the country. The objectives of the study were to ascertain the relationship between youth empowerment and employment, poverty reduction, security and employment. Survey research design was employed to accomplish the purpose of the study. Adolescent empowerment cycle theory was adopted as the theoretical framework. The target population comprised the beneficiaries of youth empowerment schemes in the study area. Both primary and secondary data sources were utilized. The data for the study were generated through structured questionnaire items. The population of the study was 139,090 while 400 sampled respondents were purposively selected from the study area. Data collected were analyzed using percentages and independent T-test using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 25. It was found among others that almost all the variables used to capture national development in Akwa Ibom state, were statistically significant except for poverty reduction and that the government has not made serious efforts to address the unemployment rate and acquisition of skills, especially for the youths. It was recommended among others that Poverty alleviation programmes should be given adequate funding and sustained by government, in order to meet the objectives for which it was established, more industries, factories and firms should be created to employ the youths and Governments at all levels must be focused on those macro and micro economic policies and programmes such as diversification and industrialization, that will ensure rapid growth and development of the economy and country at large.

Keywords: Youth Empowerment, National Development, Poverty Reduction, Security and employment.

Introduction

Youths in any society are known as the leaders of tomorrow. They play a crucial role in the prospects for development and should be included in all national development plans and programmes. Youths are the greatest assets that any nation can have. Not only are they legitimately regarded as the future leaders; they are, potentially and actually, the greatest investment for a country's development. They serve as a good measure of the extent to which a country can reproduce as well as sustain itself. The extent of their vitality, responsible conduct, and roles in society is positively correlated with the development of their country. The issue of youth empowerment and sustainable national development has taken the front burner in national discourse of many countries, especially Nigeria. This is contingent on the ground that the youths are the engine room of national development and any forward-looking nation must take cognizance of the fact that, her youth must be empowered economically, politically and social-culturally (Mboho, 2021).

History has shown time and again that the youths are dependable agents of change. Their very rebellious nature, their seeming illusions of invincibility and their fearless idealism serve as catalysts that are capable of propelling society to the apogee of development. Interestingly, nature has given the youths the gift of energy, through their young and seemingly indefatigable bodies. Empowering these seemingly indefatigable bodies requires people, programmes, institutions and systems which will provide all the youths with the support and opportunities they need to empower themselves in order to move the society forward.

If the potentials of these youths are not profitably harnessed and marshaled towards development, there is bound to be trouble (Ojikutu, 1998). Youth are filled with vigor and fresh energies which need to be properly harnessed through empowerment. This will discourage them from engaging in social vices which constrain sustainable development. The power of the youth to drive global development was recognized in 1965 by member states of the United Nations (UN) when they endorsed the declaration on the promotion among youth of the ideals of peace, mutual respect and understanding between people (United Nations, 2007).

According to Onabajo and M'Bayo (2009), national development should be man oriented and not institution oriented, that is, individually in collectiveness and not individual. To Elugbe, (1994), 'national development refers among other things, to the growth of the nation in terms of unity, education, economic well-being and mass participation in government. Development entails the provision of all the necessary materials and equipment that will guarantee that man in every society make a living and essence out of life.

Anaeto and Anaeto (2010) citing Todaro and Smith (2003), identified three objectives of development which are; 1. Increase availability and widen the distribution of basic life sustaining goods such as food, shelter, health and protection. 2. To raise levels of living in addition to higher incomes, the provision of more jobs, better education, and greater attention to cultural and human values, all of which will serve not only to enhance material well-being but also to generate greater individual and national self-esteem and 3. To expand the range of economic and social choices available to individuals and nation by freeing them from servitude and dependence, not only in relation to other people and nation states but also to the forces of ignorance and human misery. Development is the socio-cultural, political, economic and the spiritual well-being of a society. In a truly developed state, there is

assurance of good quality of life, exercise of all human rights, and freedom to participate in the democratic process. From the foregoing, development implies enhanced quality of life, equity and justice, as it takes into consideration the wellbeing, growth and advancement of individuals within the society.

Nigeria is the most populous nation in Africa and is blessed with abundant human and natural resources spread throughout the country. Despite the fact that the nations are endowed with these resources, Nigeria is still struggling to be developed and be a power to be reckoned with in the community of nations. The problem of the continuous increase in poverty, armed robbery, militancy in the Niger Delta region and Boko Haram disturbances in the Northern region may not be unconnected to the fact that majority of Nigeria youths are not empowered to contribute to national development. The belief of the youths is that the nation has failed them and therefore, they are paying back to the country what they felt was given to them (Mboho, 2011).

Unfortunately, most of our tertiary institutions turn out graduates on yearly basis without a corresponding job creation to take care of them (Nnachi, Nwigwe, & Ukoma, 2013). Youth unemployment rate is over 50 percent, meaning that about 64 million Nigerian youths are unemployed. This scourge of unemployment has deprived many Nigerian youths access to contributing their quota to national development.

It is also worthy to note that Nigeria remains the only member of the Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) that is categorized among the worlds' poorest twenty countries. (Adeola, 2011). Previous governments in Nigeria made several attempts to alleviate the poverty situation. For instance, the Gowons' regime initiated the Udoji's commission to solve the problem of poor wage of civil servants to improve their standard of living, Mutala/Obasanjo regime initiated the Operation Feed the Nation (OFN) program, Green Revolution Campaign by the Shagari regime, Directorate of Food, Roads and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI) by the Babangida regime in 1986, followed by National Directorate of Employment (NDE) in 1987, Poverty Alleviation Programme (PAP) and replaced by National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP) in 2000 and later, National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategies (NEEDS). Despite these concerted efforts by government, the poverty situation in the country seems to be getting worse.

Bondzi-Simpson (2011) was therefore right to have asserted that enforcement challenge undermines the rate of development in most African states. Until 2007, there was no separate ministry for youth development in the country. The need for sustainable development most especially in developing countries has necessitated a refocused attention on effective youth empowerment and national development. Sustainable development provides real improvements and changes in the quality of human life and conserves the vitality and diversity of the people (Ojenike, Adedokun, Odun & Ojenike, 2014)

Security is the condition of being protected physically, emotionally, psychologically as well as from other harm, attack, terror which could be considered as non-desirable. Edem (2010) defined security as assurance of the future wellbeing and freedom from threat. National security is a collection of precautions, resources and institutions built to secure a sovereign state. Providing national security for the lives and properties within a sovereign state is a vital social contract between the masses, the government and the state. It is noteworthy that the incidence of militancy in Nigeria predates the 4th Republic. Successive civilian administrations have witnessed consistent and sustained pressure from different

ethnic militias like the Movement for the Survival of Ogoni People (MOSOP), Movement for the Actualization of the Sovereign State of Biafra (MASSOB), Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger-Delta (MEND), Oodua People's Congress (OPC), Arewa Youth Consultative Forum, etc. Similar pressure and general insecurity have also accompanied the increasing spate of kidnapping in the South-East geopolitical zone, politically motivated killings by unscrupulous groups, ethno-religious uprisings in Jos, Kano, Kaduna, Bauchi, as well as the incessant and often coordinated bombings in some terrorism-infested states of northern Nigeria by the Boko Haram sect.

Statement of the Problem

One of the greatest challenges facing governments and policymakers in Africa today is how to provide opportunities for the continent's more than 200 million youths so that they can have decent lives and contribute to the economic development of their countries. Year in, year out, political aspirants in Nigeria has the generation of employment as one of their manifestoes but this is yet to be proved after about sixty-four years of existence.

However, thirteen years after the world programmes of action for the youth was initiated, youths of the developing countries, especially in Africa are faced with heavy maladies including unemployment, underemployment, illiteracy, hunger, poverty, drug abuse, moral decadence and violence and crime. They are also confronted with problems of fanaticism and cultism among others (Peters *et al.*, (2023). Millions of youths in Nigeria face bleak employment opportunities and are vulnerable shocks in labour markets (National Youth Policy 2006). Youths described in this manner cannot make any meaningful contribution to national development. Apart from being the most populous African country, Nigeria is endowed in terms of abundant deposit of crude oil, mineral resources and agricultural products to mention but a few. She is ranked the sixth richest nation in the world in terms of crude oil reserve and supply, yet her citizens are wallowing in abject poverty. This has led to an alarming rate of crime which affects sustainable national development adversely. Governments at all levels have continued to lay claim to several jobs created. Yet, the jobs are nowhere to be found by the massive youth. Dwindling economy resulting from corrupt practices, lack of entrepreneurial skills, job creations, marketable and productive skills have all been identified as the root causes of youth unemployment (Mboho, 2011).

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It is also worthy to note that Nigeria remains the only member of the Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) that is categorized among the worlds' poorest twenty countries. (Adeola, 2011). Previous governments in Nigeria made several attempts to alleviate the poverty situation by initiating different poverty alleviation programmes yet, with these concerted efforts by government, the poverty situation in the country seems to be

getting worse and meaningful objectives are yet to be achieved. (Iba, 2018).

Objectives of the study

The general objective of this study is to examine Youth Empowerment and National Development in Akwa Ibom State.

The **Specific objectives** are:

- i. To examine the relationship between Youth Empowerment and Security in Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. To determine the relationship between Youth Empowerment and Poverty Reduction in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses was tested in this study at 0.05 alpha level of significance to ascertain its level of acceptance or otherwise.

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between Youth empowerment and Employment opportunities in Akwa Ibom State.

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between Youth empowerment and Poverty Reduction in Akwa Ibom State

Review of Related Literature

Youth empowerment

Youths are the young and energetic people who are mostly referred to as the engine room of any society. The concept of youth has attracted various interpretations that have amounted to a state of controversy. This controversy arises because of the difficulty in reaching an agreement on the age bracket that should constitute the acceptable youth age. Many countries see youth as ending at the age when a person is given equal treatment under the law – often referred to as the “voting age”. In many countries, this happens when the young person is 18 years old. After this age, the young person is considered adult.

The word, “Empowerment” is commonly used to refer to a widely participatory process of directed social change in a society, intended to bring about social and material advancement including greater equality, freedom, and other valued qualities-for the majority of the people through their gaining greater control over their environment (Arvind and Everett, 1989).

Empowerment is the process of equipping one with relevant knowledge, abilities, competence and skills that will make him/her become able to take effective control of one's self and become useful (Enwo-Irem, 2009). Hornby (2016) defines empowerment in the context it is used in this paper, as to give somebody more control over their own life or the situation they are in. Empowerment can equally be defined as the act of giving power to a person or group of persons who had hitherto lacked power or authority, which will enable one take decisions and act on such decisions without any unwanted external hindrance. Therefore, it is the process of strengthening the existing capacities and capabilities of disadvantaged groups in the society to enable them perform towards improving themselves, their families, and the society as a whole. It is a multi-dimensional process involving the transformation of economic, social, psychological, political and legal circumstances of the powerless (James, 2008).

Youth empowerment therefore, is a process where children and young people are encouraged to take charge of their lives. They do this by addressing their situation and then take action in order to improve their access to resources and transform their consciousness through their belief, values, and attitudes. Youth empowerment aims to improve quality of life and is achieved through participation in youth programmes (Peters, Udoh, Akpan & Akpan, 2024). These programs can be through non-profit organizations, government organizations, schools or private organizations (Mboho, 2021).

Youth Empowerment and Poverty Alleviation

Empowerment is a critical factor for achieving poverty eradication is a plan designed to improve the economic and social life of a specific group of people in society (World Bank, 1975). People need to be made aware of their rights and entitlements, equipped with skills to make an informed choice and negotiate for their rights and have access to resources for their human development.

Ekanen (2014) opined that empowerment as a means to extend the benefits of socioeconomic and political development in the economy to the poorest among those who seek a livelihood in the rural areas. The socioeconomic development of any country is measured by the standard of living of their citizens, general welfare, and the youth empowerment. Fayemi's (2012) finding in his study carried out in Ogun state, Nigeria, shows that youth empowerment policy is the best for the alleviation of poverty among the youths in Ogun state. This indicates positive impact and relationship between the youth empowerment scheme and poverty alleviation. Similarly, in Ogun state, as the problem of poverty surfaces more youths are being empowered to tackle the problem although the finding revealed that the system is politically-influenced and biased.

Relationship between Youth Empowerment and Crime Control

Giving power through skill acquisition and amplifying the possibilities to get or create a job or business through micro-credits, access to ICT networks, is one of the best ways to fight crime and criminal elements. According to Ajufu (2013), skills acquisition as an empowering tool might help people to change the conditions of their lives by action while having knowledge and relevant skills of a trade that will make competitive in the particular productive field. This to a large extent would keep them away from crime, because their minds are activated towards positive activities. Aremu and Ahmed (2011), posit that empowering people through skills acquisition can help check crime because those who have been empowered become self-reliant and independent.

Similarly, Awogbenle and Iwuamadi (2010), noted that empowerment could be a strategy to improve the income status at the bottom line by making people aware of their potentials, which if properly harnessed would keep away poverty and criminal behaviour. Empowering people give them control and ownership of their lives, which consequently, discourages them from criminal behaviour. When youths are empowered, they see themselves as stakeholders in the development of the society they find themselves.

Youth empowerment is one of the non-violent ways of checking crime and deviant behaviour among youths. It is critical for controlling crime in any human society. The fact remains that youths should be made to be aware of the potentials they command, equip them with skills to make informed choice and negotiate for their rights, and have access to

resources for their development (Peter & Bassey, 2019). This will keep them away from crime. (Adenikinju, 2005). Empowering youths according to Akpan (2006), implies the recognition that anyone can make the difference in his/her life and other people's lives. Ekpo (2006), observed that when people are empowered, they are equipped with skills and knowledge with which they can earn a living and eschew violent crime. In this way, they will both be able to get paid employment or start up a business and earn an income that will make them avoid crime. Earning an income is the first step towards a crime free life. Empowered people can help to achieve a sustained economic growth and development through investing in income generation activities (Peters, Usoro, Ekong, & James, 2023).

Creating a system where empowered people also feel the need to empower others lead to poverty eradication and subsequently help in fighting crime (Ezeani, 2009). People who are empowered are able to achieve their goals in a much better way and that is usually the way in which the poverty cycle can be broken, which reduces the tendency for criminal behaviour (Dele and Olayinka, 2009). Empowering individuals and communities is necessary to attain equal distribution of available resources so that few do not benefit from the labour of many. The empowerment process promotes greater social and economic participation by the disadvantaged and marginalized. People who are empowered are more proficient at identifying and seizing opportunities for self-employment and fuller employment. The seizing of these opportunities creates additional income streams for households.

Theoretical Framework

The Adolescent Empowerment Cycle (AEC) (Chinman & Linney, 1998)

This model was developed by Chinman and Linney (1998) to advance the understanding of the impact of empowerment schemes on adolescent development. This model is built on the premise that empowering adolescents can help to mitigate or avert some of the social hitches facing contemporary societies. According to the proponents of AEC, the empowerment scheme can function as a preventive intervention to a number of problematic behaviours unveiled by adolescents as a result of identity crisis and formation as well as role (Amoke, 2018). Furthermore, the AEC model is a derivative of developmental and social control theories. It postulates that the empowerment programme is vital tool in the promotion of a positive, socially acceptable development process through adolescence and social bonding. This implies that engaging adolescents in varying social, economic and political activities will reduce the extent to which they get involved in negative social vices.

The introduction of empowerment schemes in contemporary Nigerian society is stimulated by the dire need for a lasting solution to the problem of unemployment and its concomitant social vices. The manifestation of youth unemployment challenges in the state and country, Nigeria led to the establishment of numerous schemes which are geared towards engaging unemployed youths in different socio-economic activities and roles (ranging from traffic management, fire service, solid waste management, information and orientation). This is with an identity crisis and formation, as well as the lack of meaningful roles that influence youth involvement in negative behaviours will be resolved. More so, development experts strongly believe that engaging the youths in varying empowerment programmes and initiatives will enable them to learn new skills, ways and manners in which they can continue meaningfully to the development process and social bond.

The introduction of empowerment schemes in contemporary Nigerian society is

stimulated by the dire need for a lasting solution to the problem of unemployment and its concomitant social vices. The manifestation of youth unemployment challenges in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria led to the establishment of Youth Empowerment schemes geared towards engaging unemployed youths in different socio-economic activities and roles. This is with a particular consciousness that when youths participate in these positive activities, the issue of identity crisis and formation, as well as the lack of meaningful roles that influence youth involvement in negative behaviours will be resolved. More so, development experts strongly believed that engaging the youths in varying empowerment programmes and initiatives will enable them to learn new skills, ways and manners in which they can contribute meaningfully to the development process and social bond.

Methodology

This study adopted the survey design. This particular method was adopted because the research attempted to determine the opinion, attitude and behavior of the beneficiaries and their instructors with respect to the phenomenon of youth empowerment programs and national development. According to Mboho (2015), surveys are usually towards the determination of status of a given phenomenon, they focus on people and their opinions, behaviours, belief and attitudes. The study carried out in Abak Local Government, Akwa Ibom State because of the youth empowerment scheme is solely run from the state capital. The data gathering is the use of a structural questionnaire with 16 items. The first section of the instrument centered on the personal data of the respondents. Section B focused on research questions 1 and it elicited for responses to which youth empowerment programmes has helped in poverty reduction and security in the country.

Adolescent empowerment cycle theory was adopted as the theoretical framework. The target population comprised the beneficiaries of youth empowerment schemes in the study area. Both primary and secondary data sources were utilized. The data for the study were generated through structured questionnaire items. The population of the study was 139,090 while 400 sampled respondents were purposively selected from the study area. Data collected were analyzed using percentages and independent T-test using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 25.

Test of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at .05 alpha level.

Research Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between youth empowerment and poverty reduction.

T-Test analysis of Youth empowerment and poverty reduction

N=380

Variables	Mean	SD	df	p-value	Sig. level	Decision
Youth empowerment	17.11	1.85				
	320	0.07		0.05	Sig.	
Poverty Reduction	34.90	2.27				

Source: Field data (2025)

The results from table1 showed that the calculated p-value 0.07 is greater than the alpha level 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis none which states that there is no significant

relationship between youth empowerment and poverty reduction in Akwa Ibom state is accepted. This implies that there is no significant relationship between youth empowerment and poverty reduction in Akwa Ibom state.

Research Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between youth empowerment and security.

T-Test analysis of Youth empowerment and security

N=380

Variables	mean	SD	df	p-value	sig. level	Decision
Youth empowerment	17.97	1.23				
	320	0.02		0.05	Sig.	
Employment	34.90	2.27				

Source: Field data (2025)

The results from table 2 shows that the calculated p-value of 0.02 is less than the alpha level 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis three which states that there is no significant relationship between youth empowerment and security is rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between youth empowerment and security.

Discussion of Findings

Test of objective one showed that there is no significant relationship between youth empowerment and poverty reduction. The implication of this findings is that since the inception of several poverty alleviation programmes by various governments in Nigeria, they have failed to reduce the poverty rate.

The result contradicts the findings of Fayemi (2012), Abdusalam (2015), Badejo, Agunyai and Adeyemi (2015), who reported that youth empowerment helped to reduce poverty among youths. This contradiction could be due to the fact that a quality measure of poverty was used in this study which captured the attributes the respondents considered as indicators of poverty as opposed to other studies which measured poverty by different approaches. Furthermore, the findings could be attributed to certain constraints faced by the scheme as reported by Inyang and Asa (2020). These constraints include low monthly stipends, high transportation cost to the venue of the programme and inadequate monitoring and evaluation of the activities of the scheme.

Test of objective three revealed that there is a significant relationship between youth empowerment and security. Youth empowerment is a channel for addressing security challenges in Nigeria. The survey has revealed that there is a high rate of unemployed youths who stay idle all day, yet must feed and take care of some essential needs. As a survival mechanism since they have no other means of attending to their immediate needs, they resort to all sorts of criminal activities ranging from armed robbery, kidnapping, burglary, murder, rape, violence and conflict, thereby heightening the security challenges. It is upon this premise that Akpan (2020) and Ajaegbu (2012) are of the opinion that youth resort to criminal activities as last option since they graduate and stay idle at home for years in addition with the prevailing high cost of living and rate of corruption in the country to justify their actions.

Conclusion

The study is on youth empowerment, wealth creation and security as key to national

development. In examining the effect of the variables of the study and their effect to national development, the paper made use of secondary data to arrive at the conclusion that, youth empowerment, wealth creation through employment, poverty alleviation and national security enhance a nation's positive and sustainable development. Thus, for a nation to attain great height, she cannot afford to malign youth empowerment in the country.

From all indications, the only solution towards youth empowerment is by creating jobs in abundance and by providing relevant occupational skills as alternative to youth restiveness and towards unemployment. This can be achieved through STE programs. The need for science and technical education should be the corner stone, which a country should rely upon and should provide its youths the opportunities to train, develop skills, abilities, understanding, working habits, and to have knowledge on useful productive bases. It is well known that insecurity is one of the greatest problems confronting Nigeria today.

Consequently, the incoming government of All Progressives Congress (APC) has prioritized security in its manifesto. Among other things, it has promised to employ an extra 100,000 police officers and establish a properly trained and equipped Federal Anti-Terrorism Multi-Agency Task Force to destroy Boko Haram and any form of insurgency; introduce an immediate pay rise and improved conditions of service for all five security agencies among others. However, it is necessary to understand the concept of security in all its ramifications, the nature and character of the Nigerian State and the major threat to national security to be able to map out a programme to promote peace and security.

No nation can achieve growth or any form of stability that will enhance socioeconomic development in an atmosphere of chronic youth unemployment. The role of Nigerian government must include the formulation of policies and laws that could help improve the economic and social wellbeing of its citizens and wealth creation. There is a need to increase jobs through small enterprises and poverty alleviation schemes.

The Nigerian youth can play critical roles in sustainable development if the energy, intelligence and resources of the youths are fully and properly utilized. The youths would need to aspire for entrepreneurship neither than conventional employment. The hope of young people can be fulfilled only under the condition of peace, in the civilized and cooperative society. Young people are full of vibrant ideas when properly motivated and sufficiently guided.

For Nigeria to attain sustainable development, she must empower youth through programs and policies that are science and technology inclined then the youth of Nigeria should be made to believe that instead of brain drain, our country can be the magnet for bright minds world over that our judicial system should be the model for fairness, promptness and incorruptibility: that our inventive can be a symbol of good governance, that our environment could be clean with abundant public services, that our youth can be like Olympic champions that we can have a percent literacy, that the per capital income can go up in geometric proportion, that we can have full employment, that we can earn the reputation of been the most transparent and honest nation, and above all, we can be the most prosperous and competitive nation in the world.

Recommendations

To ensure youth empowerment and sustainable development in Nigeria, the following are recommended:

1. Poverty alleviation programmes should be given adequate funding and sustained in order to meet the objectives for which it was established.
2. Governments should create more industries, factories and firms to employ the youths and young graduates of different professional courses of higher institutions of learning, and place more emphasis on handwork than certificates, making vocational skills and entrepreneurs thrive.
3. The earlier the government realizes that crime prevention is better and cheaper than crime control, the earlier the youths will be empowered because when they are engaged, it will better the economy and the nation.

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